

**SANITARY AND HYGIENIC REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
ORGANIZATION OF DIAGNOSTIC DEPARTMENTS OF TREATMENT
INSTITUTIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: What should be paid attention to in the construction, reconstruction and reconstruction of reception diagnostic departments of treatment and prevention institutions in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Medical supplies used in the equipment process. The sanitary-technical, sanitary-hygienic, sanitary-hygienic, and epidemic-fighting aspects of the organized institution are of particular importance in the conditions of the sanitary-epidemiological tranquility and public health service of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Sanitary rules and norms for the design, construction and operation of treatment and prevention facilities and on the approval of hygiene standards" decision.

Purpose: To find out the shortcomings in the construction and organization of treatment and preventive institutions before the construction or reconstruction of the institutions, to reduce the material damage spent on correcting the mistakes and to prevent violations of sanitary and hygiene regulations.

Key words: reconstruction, maternity complexes , hygienic requirements for the rooms, hygienic requirements for finishing the rooms, daily commute, hygienic requirements for the surfaces of the rooms.

Material and methods: Intermediate sanitary control, final sanitary control and current sanitary control, participation in land selection. Acquaintance with situational plan, master plan and explanatory letter. Review the project. After the completion of the construction works, giving a summary for the start and continuation of the work.

Result: Each hospital should have an admission or admission-diagnosis department. Reception departments should be separate for children, obstetrics, gynecology, infectious diseases, skin-genital, tuberculosis and psychiatric hospitals [1,2,3,4]. Reception rooms of other departments should be shared and located in the main building with the largest number of seats. Urgent medical care hospitals include an emergency operating room, a pre-operative room, and anesthesia equipment decontamination rooms. Entrance and exit doors, stairs and elevators in infectious disease hospitals (departments) should be separate for admission and discharge of patients [13,14,16]. Hospitals (departments) of infectious diseases must have reception boxes (isolators) for receiving patients, and their number is determined as follows depending on the number of beds in the department: up to 60 - 2 boxes; from 61 to 100 - 3 boxes; More than 100 — 3 boxes and 1 additional box for every 50 patient beds (beds) in the department [17,18,19].

Hospitals (departments) of infectious diseases are equipped with boxes and reception boxes (isolators) for the reception of children. In the department of children's infectious diseases, the number of reception boxes (isolators) should be 5 percent of the number of beds, and the number of boxes should be 3 percent [20,21,22]. A delivery room will be organized as part of the reception department of the maternity complex. The flow of patients in the reception department is regulated as follows: in anti-tuberculosis hospitals and health care hospitals - 1 reception department for 800 places; in psychiatric hospitals - 1 admission department for 600 beds; in emergency medical hospitals - 1 reception department for 150 beds; in children's and other hospitals — 1 reception department for 250 beds [4,5,6,8]. Harone1 per streamto seeroomand 1 sanitary-cleaningroomorganizeto be doneneed AcceptededepartmentroomsfieldsTable 1 according toto be it is necessary

Table 1

Hospitalsacceptededepartmentroomscompositionandarea

T/r	Roomname	Roomsarea , m ²							
		number of beds							
		3	51	10	20	30	40	50	60
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.	Lobby, waitinghall	6	12	12	16	18	20	22	24
2.	Registry	-	6	6	6	8	8	8	8
3.	Sanitation cleaningroom (allkind ofinpatientsfor)	-	sanitary network * (shower andclothesreplacemen troomto shower or bath with		3x2 12				
4.	Receive seeboxingseparatelya ccessplacewith	-	contagiousdiseaseshos pitals (eachfor one type of infectionseparately)		12+1.5				
5.	Treatmentroom	allinpatientsfor		12					
6.	Bacteriologicalanaly sisget material forroom	-	contagiousdiseasesand childrenin stationary		10				
7.	Shock chamber	-	Urgentmedicalhelpand district (city) medicineunion (TTB)		13 for 1 jacket				

		accepted departments or								
8.	Clean connection room	Urgent medical help and district (city) medicine union (TTB) accepted departments or	-	12	12	15	15	15	15	15
9.	Purulent connection room	Urgent medical help hospitals and district (city) medicine union (TTB) accepted departments or)	-	12	12	15	15	15	15	15
10.	Plastering Plaster storage room with	Urgent medical help hospitals and district (city) medicine association (TTB) accepted departments or)	-	12 +2	12 +2	12 +3	12 +3	12 +3	12 +3	12+3
11.	X-ray diagnostics room		current sanitary rules , norms and hygiene regulations according to							
12.	Urgent operating room (small operating room with	Traumatology and urgent medical help hospitals for	-	24 +8	24 +8	24 +8	24 +8	24 +1 0	24 +1 0	24+1 0
13.	Vaccination room (antirabic and to the coke hall against)	Traumatology and urgent medical help hospitals for	12							

1 4.	Express laboratory		-	12	12	12	18	18	18	18
1 5.	Departmentmanagerr oom		-	12						
1 6.	Biga nurseroom		-	12						
1 7.	Employeesroom for 1 persondoctorfor *		6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
1 8.	Sanuzel **		3x2							
1 9.	Collectionaccessorie sand disinfectants storageroom	allkind ofhospitalsfor	4							
2 0.	Diagnostic rooms		Hospitaldirectionand diagnostic equipmenttypelookingof these sanitary regulationsAccording to Annex 1 is determined .							

*Note : * 4 andfrom himmore thandoctorsfor the room area is less than 32
m²not to beneed*

*** toiletspatients(men1 for womenfor - 1)
andmedicalemployeesfortooseparatelyto beneed*

Conclusion: Based on the above, in the organization of admission diagnostic departments, the "Design, construction and operation of preventive treatment facilities" approved on January 21, 2022 and registered by the Ministry of Justice on March 4, 2022 of the Sanitary-Epidemiological Peace and Public Health Committee under the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan It is

necessary to follow the sanitary rules and norms No. 0020-22 on sanitary rules, norms and hygienic norms of

References:

1. Umurov Sh. S. SANITARY-HYGIENIC AND EPIDEMIOLOGY CHARACTERISTICS OF BRUSSELS DISEASE DISEASE DYNAMICS IN KHAMDA KIZLTEPA DISTRICT //RESEARCH. - 2023. - T. 25. – no. 1. – S. 64-69.
2. Umurov Sh. S. Osobennosti Truda Rabochikh V Selskom Hozyaystve // PRACTICALANDMEDICINETHE SCIENCESSCIENTIFICMAGAZINE . - 2023. - T. 2. – no. 10. – S. 197-201.
3. Umurov Sh. S. Zdorove Molodeji // PRACTICALANDMEDICINETHE SCIENCESSCIENTIFICMAGAZINE . - 2023. - T. 2. – no. 10. – S. 189-196.
4. Tillyashaykhov , M. N., Djanklich , S. M., Ibragimov, Sh. N., Imamov, O. A., Sabirdjanova , Z. R., &Umurov , Sh. S. (2022). RASPROSTRANENNOST KOLORECTALNOGO RAKA V REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Voprosy oncology* , 68 (S 3), 174-175.
5. Sherkuzieva , G. F., Samigova , N. R., &Umurov , Sh. S. (2022). *of the populationthe wellfrom the watersuseecological and hygienicaspects* (Doctoral dissertation, Tashkent).
6. Sherkuzieva , GuzalFakhritdinovna , NargizRaimovnaSamigova , andShamsiddinSattorovichUmurov . *of the populationthe wellfrom the watersuseecological and hygienicaspects* . Diss. Tashkent , 2022.
7. Umurov Sh. S. STUDY OF WORKING CONDITIONS OF AGRICULTURAL EMPLOYEES AND IMPLEMENTATION OF NEGATIVE FACTORS AFFECTING THE HEALTH OF EMPLOYEES TO THE GENERAL PUBLIC //RESEARCH. - 2024. - T. 30. – no. 2. - S. 151-156.

8. Sherkozieva G. F., Salomova F. I., Umurov Sh. S. Hospitalinternalinfectionproblems //TASHKENTSKAYA MEDITSINSKAYA AKADEMIYa KAFEDRA EPIDEMIOLOGIII KAZAKHSKIY NAtsIONALNYY MEDITSINSKIY UNIVERSITET IMENI SD ASFENDIYAROVA. - 2023. - S. 78.
9. Umurov Sh. S. Zdorove Molodeji //SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES. - 2023. - T. 2. – no. 10. – S. 189-196.
10. Umurov Sh. S. Osobennosti Truda Rabochikh V Selskom Hozyaystve // PRACTICALANDMEDICINETHE SCIENCESSCIENTIFICMAGAZINE . - 2023. - T. 2. – no. 10. – S. 197-201.
11. Serdanovna MI et al. Epidemiological Analysis Incidence of Workers in Flour Production //Journal of Advanced Zoology. - 2023. - T. 44.
12. Sattorovich US Physiological and Hygiene Changes in Working Conditions in a Ceramic Production Enterprise //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. - 2023. - T. 4. – no. 5. - S. 968-971.
13. Nurov.AS . Key Considerations for Assessing School Food Environments // SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES, (2023/3/30).-P. 85-87
14. Nurov.AS . Disruption of Natural Systems Affects Health // SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES, (11/15/2022).-P. 258-260
15. Nurov.AS . The Importance of Ecology for Children's Health and Well-Being // SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES, (11/15/2022).-P. 238-240
16. Nurov.AS . CHANGES IN TASTE AND FOOD INTAKE DURING THE MENSTRUAL CYCLE// Science and innovation, (2022).-P. 251-253
17. Nurov.AS . Causes of Rational Eating Disorders in Children and Adolescents // AMERICAN Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health

- Sciences. AMERICAN Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences, (2023).-P.236-239
- 18.Nurov.AS . Current Problems in Providing the Population with Clean Drinking Water // AMERICAN Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences. AMERICAN Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences, (2023).-P.240-242
- 19.Nurov.AS . The Role of Water in the Spread of Infectious and Non-Infectious Diseases // AMERICAN Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences. AMERICAN Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences, (2023).-P.243-245
- 20.Nurov.AS . Existing Problems in Providing the Population With Drinking Water Through Underground Water Sources // SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES, (2023).-P.77-79
- 21.Nurov.AS . Cleaning of Open Water Bodies From Waste Water From Production Enterprises // SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES, (2023).-P.80-82
- 22.Nurov.AS . Sanitary Protection of Water Bodies and The Process of Natural Cleaning in Water Bodies// SCIENTIFIC MAGAZINE OF PRACTICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES, (2023).-P.83-85